

Citizen science training program

Week 1: Introduction to GIS

Welcome
aboard!

- Adam Peacock – Postdoctoral Research Associate in the Institute for Sustainable Futures

Difficulty of the training

- As you will learn, G.I.S is at the heart of geographical inquiry...
- The ideas may seem complex at first... my job is to explain them to you!
- But I have designed the training to start off easy and then slowly build up to an intermediate level.

But, you will need to develop these skills further beyond the training.

Citizen science training programme

Geographic Information Systems (G.I.S)

What to expect:

<u>Week:</u>	<u>Workshop sessions:</u>	<u>Independent training practical:</u>
Week 1 (15 th May 10 - 11.30am)	Introduction to G.I.S	Introduction to QGIS – digitising and creating data
		Surgery session for practical 1 Wednesday 19th May (6-7pm)
Week 2 (22 nd May 10 – 11.30am)	Vector and Raster data	Introduction to vector data in QGIS – categorising energy usage globally!
		Surgery session for practical 2 Wednesday 26th May (6-7pm)
Week 3 (29 th May 10 – 11.30am)	G.I.S theory and principles of cartography	Practice run – manipulating and analysing mobility data!
		Surgery session for practical 3 Wednesday 2nd May (6-7pm)

More information about these workshops is below!

Purpose of the training:

- To teach you an introduction to industry relevant G.I.S skills.
- To cater empower the local community to use the power of GIS
- To add as a portfolio for potential employers!

▼ Search

Search

ex: 37.407229, -122.107162

[Get Directions](#) [History](#)

▼ Places

- My Places
 - [Sightseeing Tour](#)
Make sure 3D Buildings layer is checked
- Temporary Places
 - contours.kml

▼ Layers

[Earth Gallery >>](#)

- Primary Database
 - Borders and Labels
 - Borders
 - Labels
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Sign in

Browser

- ★ Favorites
- 🏠 Home
- C:\
- 📦 GeoPackage
- 📄 SpatiaLite
- 🗨️ PostGIS
- 📄 MSSQL
- 📄 DB2

Layers

- ☑️ 2019-02-surrey-street
- ☑️ OpenStreetMap

Layer Styling

2019-02-surrey-street

Heatmap

Color ramp

Radius 5000.00 Map Units

Maximum value Automatic

Weight points by 123 weight

Rendering quality Best Fastest

Layer Rendering

Opacity 60.0 %

Blending mode Layer Feature Normal Normal

Draw effects

Control feature rendering order

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Layers

- ▶ gpw_v4_population_count_rev11_2010...
- ▶ **population change 2010 2000**
 - Decline
 - Neutral
 - Growth
 - High Growth
- ▶ gpw_v4_population_count_rev11_2000...

Search Type to locate (Ctrl+K)

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-13.8,48.5

Scale :74498398

Magnifier 100%

Rotation 0.0 °

Render

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Browser

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 - ▶ Home
 - ▶ C:\
 - ▶ GeoPackage
 - ▶ SpatiaLite

Layers

- 2012-10-01-newyork-newyorkcity-washi...
- OpenStreetMap

What is G.I.S?

Geographic – relates to a specific place on or in relation to the Earth's surface

Information – is data to which some value or interpretation has been added. In GI, the information relates to measurements, maps, images, sounds etc. of the Earth's surface

Systems – a system designed to perform a wide range of functions on and with GI

The importance of location...

Geographic location is an important attribute of activities, policies, strategies, and plans.

Geographic problems involve an aspect of location, either in the information used to solve them, or in the solutions themselves.

Everything is located in space. Focus on the *spatial* is key to G.I.S

i.e. we need to know where things are!

1854 cholera outbreak - London

Japan Earthquake 0546 GMT

3 hours

Hawaii 1307 GMT

6 hours

9 hours

12 hours

15 hours

18 hours

21 hours

Mexico 1650 GMT

Chile 0251 GMT (12 March)

How does a Geographic Information System work?

- We collect data and look at the trends across space.
- This data is generally a singular *layer*
- We can stack these *layers* so that we can explore the world in more depth
- Maneuverability – we decide how and where layers go...

the Real World

GIS World Model

Data Slices

Imagery

Elevation

Transportation

Addresses

Boundaries

Water Features

Survey Control

Your Data

We can manipulate these layers using different processes – many of which you will learn!

Representation or reality?

- When we choose layers, how to manipulate them, we are creating a representation.
- We make active decisions about what and what not to include.
- Therefore it can never truly be reality – reality is too complicated!
- But that is okay, being selective is actually an advantage. We can be specific!

Spatial is special

- **Geographic:** the Earth's surface and near-surface
- **Spatial:** any space (not just the space of the Earth's surface)
- **Spatial Analysis:** application of techniques (in GI technology) to geographic and non-geographic spaces
- **Geospatial:** (subset of spatial, applied specifically to the Earth's surface and near-surface)

Spatial is special

- **Why is spatial special?** (Industry, hundreds of courses, millions pounds etc.)
 - Almost all human activities and decisions involve an important **geographic component**
 - Crucial to understanding both **physical** and **human geography**
 - Working with geographic information involves **unique, complex** and **difficult choices**

Information systems

Information systems help us to manage “what we know”...

organize and **store**

access and **retrieve**

manipulate and **synthesize**

apply to the solution of **problems**

Data are numbers or text (almost context-free)

raw geographic facts

- e.g., a temperature at a given location transmitted as a stream of bits
- Binary – 1,0
- **We give these spatial properties..**

Information systems store knowledge that we can use to see how the world works!

- Knowledge about how the world works is more valuable than knowledge about how it looks, because it can be used to predict!
- G.I.S is nowadays essential to making accurate predictions about a wide variety of issues!

Six parts of a GIS

Therefore...

GI technology is a combination of:

- a software product, acquired to perform well-defined functions (*GI software*)
- digital representations of aspects of world (*GI*)
- a community of people who use these tools for various purposes (the *GI community*)
- the **activity** of using GI systems to solve problems or advance science (*'doing GIS'*)

Technology is improving!

- QGIS – free, open source. Covered later in the module!
- Faster computers = more storage, better processing speeds.
- New software = new processes, better accuracy and new ideas!
- Drone technology = new methods of data acquisition.

The logo for QGIS, featuring the letters 'QGIS' in a bold, green, sans-serif font. The letter 'Q' is stylized with a 3D cube icon inside its center. The cube has an orange top face, a yellow right face, and a green front face. A white diagonal line passes through the center of the cube. The entire logo is centered within a white circle that has a dark, irregular, ink-like border.

QGIS

The fastest growing industry

- Worth \$3.2 billion in 2017
- Expected to be worth \$7.5 billion in 2025
- The most sought after skill set at the moment. Knowledge of G.I.S will get you a job instantly. I know from experience!

Risks?

- Location can be manipulated for bad as well as good
- Everything we do today, all our devices, are location tracked...
- Twitter - Dr Alex Nobajas (Keele)
- Facial recognition, IP addresses, phone tracking via apps...
- Becoming easier to capture, store and manipulate data.

Summary:

- GI Systems are systems used to handle data pertaining to geographic locations
- Information systems help us manage and interpret data
- Spatial information is important as almost all human decisions involve a spatial component
- Knowledge about how the world works is more valuable than knowledge about how it looks, because it can be used to predict